

LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS IN TEST TASKS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This study presents practical experiences with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) in creating mathematics-based tests for automated university-level examinations. Two well-known LLM-powered chat tools, ChatGPT and Perplexity Pro, were tested using identical prompts to generate a predefined set of mathematical test questions. We discuss effective prompting strategies and analyze errors in the generated outputs. Additionally, we provide a brief evaluation and offer recommendations based on our findings.

Key words

Generative AI, LLMs, GPT-4, Perplexity Pro, math tests

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) are a core technology within Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) systems in the field of Natural Language Processing. GenAI enables natural language understanding and generating new content based on the patterns learned from large amounts of data, using deep-learning techniques. Specifically, LLMs refers to deep-learning algorithms that are designed for processing and generating text in the same way as it is in human communication (Touvron et al., 2023). LLMs can perform a wide range of advanced tasks, including text summarization, mathematical reasoning, and code generation (Scarfe et al., 2024), thereby approaching human-level performance. A comprehensive review and analysis of current improvements and techniques in GenAI with a focus on their applications, including LLMs, can be found, e.g., in work of Sengar et al. (Sengar et al., 2024).

The future potential of GenAI was outlined by Kalantzis and Cope (Kalantzis & Cope, 2025): "...As Gutenberg's technologies mechanized the reproduction of written text, for the first time, Generative AI mechanizes the production of written text and derivatively, multimodal meanings. ...It sells the human collective intellect back to us." However, the fundamental mechanisms underlying their operation remain insufficiently understood, making interpretability a key focus of ongoing research. At the current stage of GenAI technology, LLMs may still produce plausible but irrational or incorrect responses due to a phenomenon known as "hallucination" (Ji et al., 2023).

The present study aimed to explore the potential and limitation of LLMs in assisting teachers with mathematics-related tasks, which is a relevant topic in AI-assisted education. We

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investigated the possibility and of the application in generating LaTeX code for constructing tasks in automated exam testing to work more efficiently.

2 Large Language Models

LLMs are built on deep learning architectures, based mostly on *transformers*. This design proposed by Vaswani et al. (Vaswani et al., 2017) brought the change of the traditional approach of utilization of recurrent and convolutional neural networks to a mechanism based solely on self-attention and positional encoding to process sequential data efficiently. A brief insight into the concept of transformers, an overview of the most known models integrated into AI-chat tools, and a formulation of prompting in AI-assisted mathematical problem-solving is given in the following section.

2.1 Generating text by transformer architecture

LLM processes text by breaking it into small units (words or subwords) – tokens – that model sequentially writes one at a time to remember prior questions and answers within a defined context window. The higher number of tokens, defining the size of context window, implies processing larger amounts of text in a single interaction. Tokens are converted into dense vector representations via the embedding layer which encodes semantic relationships between words. It is fundamental for converting raw text into a format suitable for processing by subsequent layers. Model has implemented a self-attention mechanism, which amplifies the signal for key tokens to imply how words relate to each other in a sentence, regardless of their position, and positional encoding that helps the model understand word order. The structure of feedforward neural networks allows process contextualized embeddings to generate meaningful text.

In this context, the key factor of quality of outcome is training, involving unsupervised learning on huge datasets, and fine-tuning ensured by supervised learning or reinforcement learning based on human feedback for improvement accuracy and consonance with human intent.

The special feature of more advanced LLMs is *reasoning*, designed to successfully face complex multi-layers tasks. Reasoning in GenAI refers to the model’s ability to logically process and analyze information, infer relationships, and generate coherent, contextually relevant outputs. It enables AI to solve problems, make informed decisions and generate structured responses based on input data. Currently Open AI offers o3-mini, o3-mini-high, and o1 model with reasoning (OpenAI, 2024). “Pro Search” – provided by Perplexity Pro – approaches advanced tasks with more multi-step reasoning. It goes through individual simpler parts of the task step-by-step and synthesizes in-depth answers (Perplexity, 2024). Recently introduced “Deep Research” by Perplexity involves an iterative research process via analyzing extensive sources, synthesizing findings, and producing comprehensive reports (Perplexity, 2025).

Regardless of the specific language, effective interaction with LLM-based chat tools relies on the user's ability to formulate precise and clear queries. Designing well-structured prompts to instruct the model is crucial for ensuring accurate and relevant responses. A comprehensive review of prompting techniques can be found, for example, in the work of Phoenix and Taylor (Phoenix & Taylor, 2024).

2.2 Overview of LLM-based chat assistants

Probably the most well-known generative AI large language service, developed by OpenAI, is ChatGPT (<https://chatgpt.com/>), which interacts with users through chat and generates text based on a given prompt (OpenAI, 2023). It employs large-scale models built on the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) architecture involving training a model on an extensive textual dataset and subsequently fine-tuning it for specific tasks or applications (Radford et al., 2018). The collaboration between OpenAI and Wolfram has significantly enhanced performance in mathematical problem-solving (Wolfram, 2023), particularly with the release of the Wolfram plugin for ChatGPT in the spring of 2023. This plugin enables ChatGPT to utilize Wolfram Language and Wolfram|Alpha as tools, which are automatically called within ChatGPT.

Competing tools such as *Gemini* by Google (<https://gemini.google.com/>), *Claude* by Anthropic (<https://www.anthropic.com/claude>), *Microsoft Copilot* by Microsoft Corp. (<https://copilot.microsoft.com/chats/7U8jddm7nU38g4JQurfXN>), *LLama* by Meta (<https://www.llama.com/>) and the recently launched *DeepSeek* by Hangzhou DeepSeek Artificial Intelligence Co., Ltd. and Beijing DeepSeek Artificial Intelligence Co., Ltd. (<https://www.deepseek.com/>) exhibit similar functionalities. A notable tool is *NotebookLM* by Google (<https://notebooklm.google/>) which operates on a predefined set of file types and leverages the multimodal capabilities of the Gemini AI-assistant.

A distinctive tool in this domain is *Perplexity Pro* by Perplexity AI, Inc. (<https://www.perplexity.ai/>) which integrates multiple models and has been continuously updating its features. It allows users to choose among models or engage in chat using an automatic selection mode. Additionally, several advanced reasoning modes are for choice in this environment, too.

2.3 Specific prompting for math-based problems

Mathematics, which expresses complex abstract concepts and relationships, can be regarded as a form of language. It operates within a structured system of symbols and notation, analogous to the grammatical rules of spoken languages. Advances in computational power and deep-learning algorithms have enabled the training of LLMs with significantly more parameters and on extensive datasets, allowing them to infer fundamental aspects of linguistic structures across various domains. Consequently, an LLM trained to capture mathematical rules can effectively “speak” the language of mathematics (Liu et al., 2024).

LLMs are widely recognized for their effectiveness in “zero-shot” and “few-shot” learning (Brown et al., 2020). In “zero-shot” learning, the prompt does not include any examples but directly instructs the model to perform a task. While this approach may fail for more complex tasks, large-scale training enables models such as GPTs to handle certain advanced tasks in a “zero-shot” manner. In contrast, “few-shot” prompting facilitates in-context learning by providing the model with example demonstrations within the prompt to improve results.

For mathematical problem-solving, Wei et al. (Wei et al., 2022) introduced the “Chain-of-Thought” (“CoT”) prompting technique, meaning to provide step-by-step reasoning examples to influence the model to fragment the given question and generate reasoning steps, with yielding promising results. In this context, Schorcht et al. (Schorcht et al., 2024) recently demonstrated that “CoT” and “Ask-Me-Anything” prompting techniques significantly enhance the process-related quality of GPT-supported mathematical problem-solving tasks. Additionally, Chan et al. (Chan et al., 2025) observed that “CoT” prompting contributes to

conceptual understanding and improves the quality of GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 in generating question-answer pairs across selected STEM subjects.

3 Methods

In this section, we describe the formulation of the task, employed chat-AI tools, and user's interaction with models.

A calculus problem involving derivatives of functions of a single variable, a common topic in mathematics exams, was selected to evaluate the ability of the chosen models to solve more complex, structured problems with a mathematical foundation. The task required generating a formally structured solution while incorporating rules for differentiating products, quotients, composite functions, and functions raised to the power of another function.

3.1 Used AI-chat assistants

As AI-chat assistants utilizing different LLMs, ChatGPT and Perplexity Pro were selected for this study. ChatGPT was chosen for its large-scale multimodal language model GPT-4 with its ability to automatically invoke the Wolfram module, which enhances its capability to process mathematical text.

Perplexity Pro was included in the study due to its integration of multiple LLMs, which can be used either in automatic mode (it automatically selects the most suitable model for the given task) or selected one based on the user's preference (currently GPT-4o, Claude 3.7 Sonnet, Sonar, Grok-2, and Gemini 2.0 Flash) with different modes of reasoning.

We utilized three modes of reasoning. "Pro Search" solves complex mathematical questions via the model integration of the Wolfram|Alpha engine (Perplexity, 2024). Configured in auto-mode with "Reasoning with R1", tool employs the DeepSeekR1 model which utilizes a Mixture-of-Experts architecture (Dai et.al, 2024), based on a set of smaller models which are specialized in different fields and that are activated as needed. Recently added mode of reasoning – "Deep Research" – is based on iterative analyzing extensive sources, synthesis of findings and comprehensive report writing (Perplexity, 2025).

3.2 Design of prompting

To compare the quality of models' performance and evaluate the relationship between instruction quality and the content generated, we suggested and evaluated two types of prompt formulation, based on different approaches:

- One-step prompting – "zero-shot" input, the model receives a single prompt without any examples, additional steps or corrections.
- Two-step prompting – "CoT" input, going from an abstraction to the refining the detail of the desired task.

We supposed that the two-step method allowed for iterative improvement of the output, whereas the one-step approach would be faster but with a higher risk of inaccuracies.

According to Frieder et al. (Frieder et al., 2023), the largest datasets – including those containing mathematical content – are predominantly in English. As a result, mathematical outputs (such as analyzing mathematical questions and solving problems) tend to be most accurate in English. To assess the performance of different LLMs from this perspective, the automatic generation of math tasks was in both Slovak and English.

3.2.1 One-step prompting

The initial input was highly detailed and precise, instructing the model to perform the desired task in a single step. It explicitly required verification of accuracy and compliance with all specified criteria.

The formulation of input in English (correspondingly in Slovak) was as follows:

“You are a university mathematics teacher. You need to evaluate students' knowledge of mathematics, specifically the topic of the derivative of a function of a single variable. Create a test with 5 mathematical problems. The test must include the derivative of a product, a quotient, a composite function, and a function raised to the power of another function. Test must include the derivative of a function raised to another function dependent on x . Use the functions $\cos(3x-\pi)$, $\text{tg}(x^2-5)$, $2^{(4x-7)}$, $\ln(2x^4+3)$ in 3 of 5 tasks in this test. Each problem in the test should be unique and as different from the others as possible. Assign four answer choices to each problem, with only one correct answer, placed in random order. Avoid sec expression in the answers. Mark the correct answer for each problem. Verify the correctness of derivatives and the fulfilling of the test requirements. “

3.2.2 Two-step prompting

The initial input was formulated in a general manner to establish context. After reviewing the initial output, a second prompt was provided to refine the response by addressing errors, modifying specific attributes of the test, and ensuring all requirements were met.

The formulation of inputs in English (in Slovak, resp.) was as follows:

1. “Create a test with 5 math problems on the derivative of a function of one variable. Assign 4 answers to each task, of which only one is correct, in random order. The test must include the derivative of a product, a quotient, a compound function, and a function raised to the power of a function.”
„Vytvor test s 5 matematickými úlohami na deriváciu funkcie jednej premennej. Každéj úlohe prirad' 4 odpovede, z nich iba jedna je správna, v náhodnom poradí. Test musí obsahovať deriváciu súčinu, podielu, zloženej funkcie a funkcie umocnenej na funkciu.”
2. “Use the functions $\cos(3x-\pi)$, $\text{tg}(x^2-5)$, $2^{(4x-7)}$, $\ln(2x^4+3)$ in this test. A function on a function must contain x in the exponent. In the derivation of tg , let it be \cos , not sec . Mark the correct answers. ”
„Použi v tomto teste aj funkcie $\cos(3x-\pi)$, $\text{tg}(x^2-5)$, $2^{(4x-7)}$, $\ln(2x^4+3)$. Funkcia umocnená na funkciu musí v základe aj v exponente obsahovať funkciu x . V derivácii tg nech je \cos , nie sec .”

3.3 The evaluation of outcomes and generating LaTeX code

All outcomes were evaluated by a subject-matter expert using a methodology that assessed individual components related to the form and correctness of the content. The evaluations were then summarized into a total score reflecting the acceptability of the results.

We focused on four key attributes of “good” test generation:

- Fulfilling the Formal Requirements (FFR): Ensuring the task met the requirements specified in the prompt.
- Existence of Correct Answers (ECA): Verifying that correct answers were provided.
- Suitability of Distractors (SD): Assessing the quality of distractor options.
- Marking the Correct Answer as Correct (MCAC): Ensuring the correct answer was accurately marked.

Each of these four categories was evaluated on a binary scale (fulfilled =1, unfulfilled = 0). Additionally, the evaluation of ECA and MCAC was based on the proportion of acceptable partial outcomes related to the answers in each test task. Each category was equally weighted (25%). The total success score was calculated using a weighted sum method.

For practical application, the acceptable set of math tasks can be translated into LaTeX code. After that, several small improvements and corrections may be necessary to prepare code for integration with the task editor module in the Academic Information System (AIS).

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Practical demonstration of using LLM in test tasks developing

As a demonstration of the practical application of LLM implementation to the math test tasks generating, the direct outcome of experiment based on one-step prompting (in English language performing by ChatGPT employing model GPT-4 (web version of 24-February-2025) is presented in Fig.1- Fig.3. The output included a set of tasks with the verification of solutions (Fig.1, Fig.2), and the final check of the user requirements (Fig.3).

Fig.1: One-step prompting – the output in the form of test tasks set from GPT-4 – part1.

Test on Derivatives of a Function of a Single Variable

Each question has four answer choices, with only one correct answer. The test includes derivatives of products, quotients, composite functions, and a function raised to another function dependent on x . The specified functions $\cos(3x - \pi)$, $\tan(x^2 - 5)$, 2^{4x-7} , and $\ln(2x^4 + 3)$ appear in three problems. Sec expressions are avoided.

Problem 1: Derivative of a Product

Find the derivative of the function:

$$f(x) = x^2 \cos(3x - \pi)$$

A) $2x \cos(3x - \pi) - 3x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$ ✓
 B) $2x \cos(3x - \pi) + 3x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$
 C) $x^2 \cos(3x - \pi) - 6x \sin(3x - \pi)$
 D) $2x \cos(3x - \pi) - 6x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$

Verification:
 Using the product rule:

$$(fg)' = f'g + fg'$$

where $f(x) = x^2$ and $g(x) = \cos(3x - \pi)$, we get:

$$2x \cos(3x - \pi) - 3x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$$

which matches answer A. ✓

↓

Problem 2: Derivative of a Quotient

Find the derivative of the function:

$$g(x) = \frac{\tan(x^2 - 5)}{x + 1}$$

- A) $\frac{2x}{(x+1)\cos^2(x^2-5)} - \frac{\tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$ ✓
- B) $\frac{2x}{(x+1)\sin^2(x^2-5)} - \frac{\tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$
- C) $\frac{2x \tan(x^2-5)}{x+1}$
- D) $\frac{\tan(x^2-5)}{x+1} - \frac{2x}{\cos^2(x^2-5)}$

Verification:

Using the quotient rule:

$$\left(\frac{f}{g}\right)' = \frac{f'g - fg'}{g^2}$$

where $f(x) = \tan(x^2 - 5)$ and $g(x) = x + 1$, we get:

$$\frac{2x}{(x+1)\cos^2(x^2-5)} - \frac{\tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$$

which matches answer A. ✓

Fig.2: One-step prompting – the output in the form of test tasks set from GPT-4 – part2.

Problem 3: Derivative of a Composite Function

Find the derivative of the function:

$$h(x) = \ln(2x^4 + 3)$$

- A) $\frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$ ✓
- B) $\frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3}$
- C) $\frac{2x^4+3}{8x^3}$
- D) $\frac{8x^3}{2x^4-3}$

Verification:

Using the chain rule:

$$(\ln u)' = \frac{u'}{u}$$

where $u = 2x^4 + 3$, we get:

$$\frac{8x^3}{2x^4 + 3}$$

which matches answer A. ✓

Problem 4: Derivative of a Function Raised to Another Function

Find the derivative of the function:

$$k(x) = (x^2 + 1)^x$$

- A) $(x^2 + 1)^x \left(\frac{2x^2}{x^2+1} + \ln(x^2 + 1) \right)$ ✓
 B) $x(x^2 + 1)^{x-1} (2x + \ln(x^2 + 1))$
 C) $(x^2 + 1)^x \left(\frac{2x}{x^2+1} + \ln(x^2 + 1) \right)$
 D) $x(x^2 + 1)^{x-1} \ln(x^2 + 1)$

Verification:

Using logarithmic differentiation:

$$y = (x^2 + 1)^x$$

Taking the natural logarithm:

$$\ln y = x \ln(x^2 + 1)$$

Differentiating both sides:

$$\frac{y'}{y} = \frac{2xx}{x^2 + 1} + \ln(x^2 + 1)$$

Multiplying by y :

$$y' = (x^2 + 1)^x \left(\frac{2x^2}{x^2 + 1} + \ln(x^2 + 1) \right)$$

which matches answer A. ✓

Fig.3: One-step prompting – the output in the form of test tasks set from GPT-4 – part3.

Problem 5: Derivative of an Exponential Function

Find the derivative of the function:

$$p(x) = 2^{4x-7}$$

- A) $4 \cdot 2^{4x-7} \ln 2$ ✓
 B) $2^{4x-7} \ln 4$
 C) $2^{4x-7} \ln 2$
 D) $4 \cdot 2^{4x-7}$

Verification:

Using the derivative formula:

$$(a^u)' = a^u \ln a \cdot u'$$

where $a = 2$ and $u = 4x - 7$, we get:

$$p'(x) = 2^{4x-7} \ln 2 \cdot 4 = 4 \cdot 2^{4x-7} \ln 2$$

which matches answer A. ✓

Final Check of Test Requirements:

- ✓ Includes required derivative types:
 - Product Rule: Problem 1
 - Quotient Rule: Problem 2
 - Composite Function (Chain Rule): Problems 3 & 5
 - Function Raised to Another Function: Problem 4
- ✓ Includes specified functions:
 - $\cos(3x - \pi)$ in Problem 1
 - $\tan(x^2 - 5)$ in Problem 2
 - 2^{4x-7} in Problem 5
 - $\ln(2x^4 + 3)$ in Problem 3
- ✓ Each problem is unique and different from others.
- ✓ No sec expressions are used in answers.
- ✓ All derivatives are verified and correct.

This is a complete and accurate test. Let me know if any modifications are needed! 😊

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As can be seen, according to the proposed evaluation methodology, this outcome is excellent in terms of both form and content. The outstanding performance of the model used can be explained by some of the several factors:

1. The model's advanced capabilities, enhanced by the integration of the Wolfram plugin and extensive large-scale training.
2. The highly detailed and precise formulation of the prompt written in English.

Fig.4: Part of the LaTeX code generated by ChatGPT (model GPT-4)

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Here is the LaTeX code for the test, formatted properly for a document:

latex 📄 Kopírovat 🔄 Upravit

\documentclass{article}
\usepackage{amsmath}

\begin{document}

\title{Test on Derivatives of a Function of a Single Variable}
\author{University Mathematics Department}
\date{}
\maketitle

Each question has four answer choices, with only one correct answer. The test includes deriva

\section*{Problem 1: Derivative of a Product}
Find the derivative of the function:
\[
f(x) = x^2 \cos(3x - \pi)
\]
\begin{itemize}
\item (A)  $2x \cos(3x - \pi) - 3x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$  \quad \textbf{(Correct)}
\item (B)  $2x \cos(3x - \pi) + 3x^2 \sin(3x - \pi)$ 

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3. The explicit inclusion of instructions to verify correctness and ensure compliance with test requirements.
4. The model's memory, which retained information from previous outputs.

To apply the results in the next phase of test task development within the task editor module in the Academic Information System (AIS), we asked the AI to generate LaTeX code. A selected piece of the code is shown in Fig. 4. The relevant rows of LaTeX code can then be pasted into the test task editor in AIS (see Fig. 5).

Fig.5: Generation math expressions in task editor module

4.2 Other trials generating outcomes with deficiencies

All other trials, in both English and Slovak, mostly exhibited deficiencies either in form or content. In this section, we analyze these outcomes using the suggested evaluation methodology.

One-step prompting outputs

The outcome of ChatGPT powered by model GPT-4 for the Slovak version of the test was acceptable, except the failure related to the instruction to avoid the secant function.

Perplexity Pro (web version of 25-February-2025) set to automatic mode with "Deep Research" reasoning and to Gemini 2.0 Flash and Claude 3.7 Sonnet models with "Reasoning

with R1” provided excellent results with similar features regardless of the language. However, in all these outputs, the secant function was expressed using an identity not commonly used.

Two-step prompting outputs

After the first prompt, no LLM produced fully satisfactory results, regardless of the instruction language. The most frequent issues included:

- Missing or unmarked correct answers.
- Incorrect answers marked as correct.
- Absence of the derivative of a function raised to another function.
- Use of the secant function in tangent derivatives, which is not taught in basic math.
- Distractors with two correct answers, but only one marked (AI corrected this with reasoning when given feedback in the Slovak version, see Appendix A).

The updated requirements in the second prompt introduced new demands and addressed the mistakes and unsatisfactory parts of the previous outcome. Despite the feedback, both tools generating tests with repeated or new issues (Appendix B and C), including:

- Identical, correct answers.
- Missing correct answers or incorrect ones marked.
- Inappropriate distractors and failure to avoid the secant function (Slovak test).
- Incorrect handling of derivatives of a function raised to another function (both versions).

Tab. 1 compares the quality of results after two-step (“CoT”) prompting with total scores calculated for each selected tool. No language consistently outperformed the other, and both failed with complex tasks. Perplexity Pro performed best in English achieving the highest score in “Deep Research” reasoning configuration. Overall, based on the total score, both AI-chat tools demonstrated similar capabilities related to the evaluation of the studied task.

Tab. 1 Comparison of selected tools in the success rate of the second outcome in two-step (“CoT”) prompting

AI-chat tool	ChatGPT	ChatGPT	Perplexity Pro	Perplexity Pro	Perplexity Pro	Perplexity Pro
Model/ Metrics	GPT -4 (English)	GPT -4 (Slovak)	Auto-mode “Pro Search” Reasoning) (English)	Auto-mode “Pro Search” Reasoning (Slovak)	Auto-mode “Deep Research” Reasoning (English)	Auto-mode “Deep Research” Reasoning (Slovak)
FFR	1	1	1	0	1	1
ECA	3/5	4/5	4/5	4/5	5/5	4/5
SD	1	1	1	0	1	0
MCAC	2/5	4/5	4/5	4/5	5/5	4/5
Total Score	0.75	0.90	0.90	0.40	1	0.65

4.3 Proposal of the workflow for the implementation of LLM to the effective test tasks development

Despite issues with answer’s correctness, based on the practical experience outlined above, the following steps can offer the effectiveness of developing math tests in AIS through the utilization of LLMs:

1. Write a prompt specifying the conditions for the test tasks.
2. Check the correctness and suitability of the obtained results.
3. Revise the prompt or add more specific details to improve clarity of instruction.
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until you are satisfied with the generated result.
5. Ask LLM to generate the corresponding LaTeX code for the test.
6. Paste the appropriate rows of LaTeX code into the test task editor in AIS, for both the questions and the answers.
7. Review the result as it will appear to students.

Educators can mitigate errors in AI-generated tests by conducting a systematic manual review and verification of all questions and answers to ensure accuracy, with a prompt refining hand in hand. By employing “CoT” prompting, the “human-in-the-loop” approach, which integrates both oversight and feedback, serves as an efficient strategy for improving overall performance. Additionally, using tools with more advanced algorithms (e.g., like these implementing reasoning) can yield more reliable outcomes.

As the one-step (“zero-shot”) prompting demonstrated its potential of the competent results in this study, we recommend formulating instructions for the model very precisely in a single interaction and including a self-verification instruction to ensure the high-quality outcome. The key is to deliver the exact message specification, provided with as many details as possible to maneuver the model providing the desired result.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we presented the potential of selected generative AI tools for the effective generating test tasks related to calculus for automated math exams. By employing two modes of prompting and using identical prompts written in both English and the local (Slovak) languages, we compared a set of test tasks generated by different LLMs in ChatGPT and Perplexity Pro AI-assistants. An analysis of the acceptability of the generated outcomes showed that GPT-4 and DeepSeek-R1 model using one-step (“zero-shot”) prompting with English in the prompt were successful in the rapid generating the high-quality tests. This result can be attributed to the use of the large-scale trained model with advanced reasoning mode, utilized the Wolfram plugin, a very precise prompt with a self-verification request, and instructions provided directly in English.

The main limitation of the instant applying generative AI for math test generation is the need of human supervision to ensure that all requirements specified in the prompt are met. The model’s responses can be unstable and unpredictable, making the outcomes potentially unreliable. Despite this, teachers can reduce detected errors in tests generated by AI via implementing manual review, validation, and prompts refining. Based on our practical experience, we found that with a brief revision process, the obtained set of tasks could be adapted for further work with LaTeX code in the information system, thereby enhancing the efficiency of creating tests for automated math exams.

As LLMs continue to evolve rapidly, ongoing advancements are expected. Consequently, the findings of this study reflect the current state of the technology and may not be fully reproducible in the future. Future research will explore the application of LLMs in another areas such as statistics and design of experiments, with a focus on refining prompt clarity, evaluating a broader range of models, and implementing “few-shot” technique methodology.

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7 Resources

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8 Appendix A

Reasoning ChatGPT with GPT-4 for fixing the mistake

Prečo odpoveď 1b nie je správna?

Pozrime sa podrobnejšie na deriváciu funkcie $f(x) = x^2 \sin x$.

Použijeme **pravidlo pre deriváciu súčinu**:

$$(fg)' = f'g + fg'$$

Tu máme:

- $f(x) = x^2 \rightarrow f'(x) = 2x$
- $g(x) = \sin x \rightarrow g'(x) = \cos x$

Podľa pravidla:

$$(x^2 \sin x)' = 2x \sin x + x^2 \cos x$$

Teraz skontrolujme odpoveď (B) $x^2 \cos x + 2x \sin x$:

- Porovnajme so správnym výsledkom $2x \sin x + x^2 \cos x$.
- Odpoveď (B) je síce správne vypočítaná, ale nie je v rovnakom poradí, ako som pôvodne uviedol v správnej odpovedi (C).

Technicky vzaté, odpoveď (B) je tiež správna, pretože sčítanie je komutatívne. Takže by si ju mohol považovať za správnu rovnako ako (C). To bola len moja chyba v označení správnej odpovede – vďaka za všímavosť! 😊

9 Appendix B

Two-step prompting in Slovak, the final output generated by GPT 4

Ďakujem za trpezlivosť! Teraz už správne zohľadním všetky tvoje požiadavky:

1. Použijem cos v derivácii tg.
2. Funkcia na funkciu bude mať x v exponentoch.
3. Všetky požiadavky budú splnené a test bude mať stále 5 úloh.

TEST: Derivácia funkcie jednej premennej

1. Určte deriváciu funkcie

$$f(x) = (3x^2 + 5x) \cos(3x - \pi)$$

- A) $(6x + 5) \cos(3x - \pi) - 3(3x^2 + 5x) \sin(3x - \pi)$ ✓
- B) $(6x + 5) \cos(3x - \pi) + 3(3x^2 + 5x) \sin(3x - \pi)$
- C) $(6x + 5) \sin(3x - \pi) - 3(3x^2 + 5x) \cos(3x - \pi)$
- D) $6x + 5$

2. Určte deriváciu funkcie

$$g(x) = \frac{\operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{x - 3}$$

- A) $\frac{2x \cdot \frac{1}{\cos^2(x^2 - 5)}(x - 3) - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{(x - 3)^2}$ ✓
- B) $\frac{2x \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{(x - 3)^2}$
- C) $\frac{2x \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{(x - 3)}$
- D) $\frac{2x \cdot \frac{1}{\cos^2(x^2 - 5)}(x - 3) - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{(x - 3)^2}$

3. Určte deriváciu zloženej funkcie

$$h(x) = 2^{4x-7}$$

- A) $4 \cdot 2^{4x-7} \ln 2$ ✓
- B) $2^{4x-7} \ln 4$
- C) $2^{4x-7} \ln 2$
- D) $8 \cdot 2^{4x-7} \ln 2$

4. Určte deriváciu funkcie na funkciu

$$k(x) = (\ln(2x^4 + 3))^x$$

- A) $(\ln(2x^4 + 3))^x \left(\frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3} + \ln(\ln(2x^4 + 3)) \right)$ ←
- B) $x(\ln(2x^4 + 3))^{x-1} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
- C) $(\ln(2x^4 + 3))^x \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
- D) $x(\ln(2x^4 + 3))^x \cdot \frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3}$

5. Určte deriváciu funkcie

$$m(x) = e^{\cos(3x-\pi)}$$

- A) $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) e^{\cos(3x-\pi)}$
- B) $\cos(3x - \pi) e^x$
- C) $e^{\cos(3x-\pi)}$
- D) $3 \sin(3x - \pi) e^{\cos(3x-\pi)}$

Two-step prompting in English, the final output generated by GPT 4

Math Test: Derivatives of Functions of One Variable

Instructions:

Choose the correct answer for each question. Only one answer is correct.

1. Find the derivative of $f(x) = (x^2 + 3x)(\cos(3x - \pi))$.

- A. $2x + 3 - 3(x^2 + 3x) \sin(3x - \pi)$ ←
- B. $(2x + 3) \cos(3x - \pi) - 3(x^2 + 3x) \sin(3x - \pi)$
- C. $(2x + 3) \cos(3x - \pi) + 3(x^2 + 3x) \sin(3x - \pi)$
- D. $(2x + 3) \sin(3x - \pi) - 3(x^2 + 3x) \cos(3x - \pi)$

2. Find the derivative of $g(x) = \frac{\tan(x^2-5)}{x+1}$.

- A. $\frac{2x \cos^2(x^2-5)(x+1) - \tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$
- B. $\frac{2x \cos^2(x^2-5)(x+1) + \tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$
- C. $\frac{2x \cos(x^2-5)(x+1) - \tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$ ←
- D. $\frac{2x \cos(x^2-5)(x+1) + \tan(x^2-5)}{(x+1)^2}$

3. Find the derivative of $h(x) = 2^{4x-7}$.

- A. $2^{4x-7} \ln 2$
B. $4 \cdot 2^{4x-7} \ln 2$ ✓
C. $4 \cdot 2^{4x-7}$
D. $2^{4x-7} \ln(4x - 7)$
-

4. Find the derivative of $k(x) = \ln(2x^4 + 3)$.

- A. $\frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$ ✓
B. $\frac{8x^4}{2x^4+3}$
C. $\frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3}$
D. $\frac{8x^3}{x^4+3}$
-

5. Find the derivative of $m(x) = x^{\cos x}$.

- A. $x^{\cos x} (\cos x \ln x - \sin x)$ ✓ ←
B. $x^{\cos x} (\cos x + \sin x)$
C. $x^{\cos x} (\cos x \ln x + \sin x)$
D. $x^{\cos x} (\cos x - \sin x)$

11 Appendix C

Two-step prompting in Slovak, the final output generated by Perplexity Pro (Auto-mode, “Pro Search” reasoning).

Perplexity

Upravil som test podľa vašich požiadaviek. Test stále obsahuje 5 úloh, ale teraz zahŕňa funkcie, ktoré ste špecifikovali. Zachoval som rôzne typy derivácií a upravil som úlohy tak, aby spĺňali vaše dodatočné kritériá.

Test derivácií

1. Derivácia súčinu: $\frac{d}{dx} [\cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3)]$

- a) $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4 + 3}$
- b) $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4 + 3} + 2$ ←
- c) $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4 + 3} - 1$
- d) $-3 \cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \sin(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4 + 3}$

2. Derivácia podielu: $\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{\operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5)}{2^{(4x - 7)}} \right]$

- a) $\frac{2x \sec^2(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} 4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x - 7)})^2}$ ←
- b) $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} 4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x - 7)})^2}$
- c) $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} 4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x - 7)})^2} + 1$
- d) $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} - \operatorname{tg}(x^2 - 5) 2^{(4x - 7)} 4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x - 7)})^2} - 2$

3. Derivácia zloženej funkcie: $\frac{d}{dx}[e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)}]$
- a) $e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)} \cdot 2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5)$
- b) $e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)} \cdot 2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) + 3$
- c) $e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)} \cdot 2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) - 1$
- d) $e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)} \cdot 2x \sec^2(x^2 - 5)$ ←
4. Derivácia funkcie na funkciu: $\frac{d}{dx}[(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)}]$
- a) $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}\right)$
- b) $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}\right) + 2$
- c) $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}\right) - 1$
- d) $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \sin(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}\right)$
5. Derivácia súčinu: $\frac{d}{dx}[2^{(4x-7)} \ln(2x^4 + 3)]$
- a) $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2) \cdot \ln(2x^4 + 3) + 2^{(4x-7)} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
- b) $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2) \cdot \ln(2x^4 + 3) + 2^{(4x-7)} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} + 1$
- c) $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2) \cdot \ln(2x^4 + 3) + 2^{(4x-7)} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} - 2$
- d) $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2) \cdot \ln(2x^4 + 3) + 2^{(4x-7)} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} + \frac{1}{2}$

Správne odpovede:

1. a) $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
2. b) $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2-5) 2^{(4x-7)} - \text{tg}(x^2-5) 2^{(4x-7)} 4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x-7)})^2}$
3. a) $e^{\text{tg}(x^2-5)} \cdot 2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5)$
4. a) $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}\right)$
5. a) $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2) \cdot \ln(2x^4 + 3) + 2^{(4x-7)} \cdot \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$

Tento test teraz zahŕňa požadované funkcie a spĺňa všetky vaše kritériá, vrátane použitia \cos^{-2} namiesto \sec^2 v derivácii tg a funkcie umocnenej na funkciu s funkciou x v základe aj v exponente.

Two-step prompting in English, the final output generated by Perplexity Pro (Auto-mode, “Pro Search” reasoning).

✿ Perplexity

I've revised the test to incorporate the functions you specified while maintaining 5 tasks. I've also used cos instead of sec in the derivation of tg as requested. Here's the updated test with marked correct answers:

Calculus Test: Derivatives

- Find the derivative of the product: $\frac{d}{dx} [\cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3)]$
 - $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$ ✓
 - $-3 \cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \sin(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
 - $3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
 - $-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3}$
- Calculate the derivative of the quotient: $\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{\text{tg}(x^2-5)}{2^{(4x-7)}} \right]$
 - $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)} - \text{tg}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)}4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x-7)})^2}$ ✓
 - $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)} + \text{tg}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)}4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x-7)})^2}$
 - $\frac{x \cos^{-2}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)} - \text{tg}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)}4 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x-7)})^2}$
 - $\frac{2x \cos^{-2}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)} - \text{tg}(x^2-5)2^{(4x-7)}2 \ln(2)}{(2^{(4x-7)})^2}$
- Find the derivative of the composite function: $\frac{d}{dx} [2^{(4x-7)}]$
 - $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4 \ln(2)$ ✓
 - $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 2 \ln(2)$
 - $2^{(4x-7)} \cdot 4$
 - $4 \cdot 2^{(4x-7)}$
- Determine the derivative of the function raised to a power: $\frac{d}{dx} [(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)}]$
 - $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} \right)$ ✓
 - $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \cos(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \sin(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} \right)$
 - $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) - \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} \right)$
 - $(\cos(3x - \pi))^{\ln(2x^4+3)-1} \cdot \left(-3 \sin(3x - \pi) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \cos(3x - \pi) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3} \right)$
- Calculate the derivative: $\frac{d}{dx} [\text{tg}(x^2 - 5) \ln(2x^4 + 3)]$
 - $2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \text{tg}(x^2 - 5) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$ ✓
 - $x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \text{tg}(x^2 - 5) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$
 - $2x \cos^{-2}(x^2 - 5) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \text{tg}(x^2 - 5) \frac{4x^3}{2x^4+3}$
 - $2x \cos^{-1}(x^2 - 5) \ln(2x^4 + 3) + \text{tg}(x^2 - 5) \frac{8x^3}{2x^4+3}$

This test now incorporates the functions $\cos(3x-\pi)$, $\text{tg}(x^2-5)$, $2^{(4x-7)}$, and $\ln(2x^4+3)$ as requested. The correct answers are marked with a ✓ symbol. The test still covers various types of derivatives, including product rule, quotient rule, chain rule, and the derivative of a function raised to the power of another function.

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